

PERLOCUTIONARY ACTS AND COOPERATIVE PRINCIPLE ADHERENCE IN SELECTED PHILIPPINE PUBLIC SERVICE INTERVIEWS

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Abstract

Public service programs have been prevalent in Philippine broadcast media since television and began. With the prevalence of social media as part of the modernization of mass media, there are now emergent public service programs that air both on traditional media and social media. Anchored on Searle and Austin's Speech Act Theory framework as well as Grice's Cooperative Principle framework, the study by Ramos utilized trending interviews over "Wanted sa Radyo" as samples. It was revealed that persuasion and convincing were two of the most prevalent perlocutionary acts for both the hosts and the guests. Focusing on the Gricean maxims, the most adhered maxims were of relevance and manner; however, it was also discovered that manner also had the most violations. Further research on local public service talk shows with respect to speech acts and maxims was recommended by the author for scholars on sociolinguistics and discourse analysis.

Keywords: *Cooperative Principle, critical discourse analysis, Gricean maxims, media discourse, speech acts*

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INTRODUCTION

Public service programs in the Philippines have been existent since the beginning of radio and television broadcasting for more than half a century now. These programs are meant to serve as auxiliaries and intermediaries for both governmental and non-governmental organizations and agencies and the public. One of the objectives of public service programs is to assist indigent people by providing them with links to concerned agencies that can help them with their complex problems; examples of these problems are medical-related, crime-related, and other similar concerns. Another objective of public service programs is to provide its guests with assistance and advice in order that they would be motivated to solve their problems, regardless of their location or social status. A last objective of such programs, especially in the present, is to admonish transgressors such as accused parties and incompetent entities (e.g. businesses, government agencies, and other similar institutions) for them to apologize to the aggrieved parties and to respond promptly to the problems they were responsible for causing..

Public service programs are basically broadcast talk shows, which **Hutchby (2006)** defines as a medium that basically employs conversations, which are mainly conversational and natural in nature, with figures of speech at times used for eliciting interest (**Hirsch, 2015**). He adds that talk shows have various functions, which are to seek information, share experiences, state opinions, and even teach concepts and life lessons. There are episodes in numerous talk shows that employ questions, Hutchby further avers, which have the following objectives: a) to seek opinions of viewers b) to encourage recall of what has happened in the past, c) to encourage critical thinking among audiences, and d) to attract more audiences through probing and sensationalism. **Dixon and Spee (2003)** expound that television talk shows serve as an avenue for exchange of emotions and ideas among guests, with hosts serving as moderators. **Petričková (2012)** categorizes talk shows into two types: a) Institutional talk and b) Celebrity and political interviews. Institutional talk shows focus on human interest and problem resolution while celebrity and political interviews focus on personalities and their activities, as well as their sentiments. Public service programs belong to the institutional talk type because they focus on assisting guests with their various concerns.

The researcher anchored his study on two frameworks: a) **Speech Act Theory** by Austin and Searle (in **Maharani, Mujiyanto, & Warsono, 2020**; in **Karmila, Rohmena, & Aderlaepe, 2019**) and b) **Cooperative Principle** by **Grice (1975)**. The Speech Act Theory consists of locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary acts, the latter of which is one of the focuses of the current study. Speech acts can be direct or indirect, depending on the exchange between or among interlocutors (**Tressyalina & Ridwan, 2015**). Perlocutionary acts refer to the intended effect of an utterance by a locutor on his/her interlocutor/s. They also elicit results and are actually performative because an utterance has either positive or negative consequences on the part of someone being spoken to and who acts as the listener simultaneously. **Kang (2013)** illustrates that there are two kinds of perlocutionary effects, namely the actual motive of the locutor that leads to an utterance and the actual result. The actual motives and actual results are sometimes inconsistent because there are times when results are negative or unintended. Yule (in **Kang, 2013**; **Yang, 2014**) agrees that there are times when misunderstandings occur due to failure to understand contexts and interlocutors. As for the Cooperative Principle (**Grice, 1975**), it pertains to following certain rules in conversations to ensure that exchanges result in positive effects (**Zebua, Rukmini, & Saleh, 2017**; **Hirsch, 2015**). In the Cooperative Principle Theory, there are instances when maxims are followed, flouted, or violated (**Yang, 2014**; **Tressyalina & Ridwan, 2015**). Following refers to complying with the maxims within the Cooperative Principle. On the other hand, flouting refers to inadvertent non-compliance with any of the

maxims, reasons of which can be eliciting humor (**Dixon & Spee, 2003**), failure to understand an interlocutor's statement or message, or making an interlocutor determine hidden messages behind one's utterance. As for violating, it pertains to deliberately disobeying any or most (or all) of the four maxims; violating is done by an interlocutor for various reasons, both implied and overt (**Sobhani & Saghebi, 2014; Rohaniyah, 2013**).

Studies on television interviews and on face-to-face interviews, including one doctor-patient interaction, have been conducted in relation to both perlocutionary acts and cooperative principles. **Sobhani and Saghebi (2014)** examined perlocutionary acts and common maxim violations as reflected in utterances of patients who consult psychiatrists and other allied medical professionals. **Tressyalina and Ridwan (2015)** conducted a study on speech acts among hosts and guests of an Indonesian primetime talk show. In relation to Tressyalina and Ridwan's study, **Karmila, Rohmana, and Aderlaepe (2019)** studied the perlocutionary acts of another primetime Indonesian talk show, focusing also on hosts and guests. **Fadhly (2012)** and **Mustapha (2017)** did separate studies on maxim flouting by high-ranking political leaders, with Fadhly focusing on then-president of Indonesia Susilo Bambang Yudhyono and Mustapha on then-prime minister of Malaysia Najib Razak and opposition leader Anwar Ibrahim. **Rosyidah (2013)** also did a similar study, in which she investigated instances of flouting and violation of maxims in political interviews. **Febriyani (2019)** examined instances of flouting of maxims in a CNN interview featuring Turkiye president Recep Tayyip Erdogan. Focusing on political interviews in Israel, **Hirsh (2015)** delved on maxim violations by politicians and hosts through their use of irony, sarcasm, and other similar communicative tools. **Yang (2014)** focused on cooperative principle flouting and violation within the context of a Chinese talk show that featured politicians, athletes, and performing artists. In the western context, **Clementson (2018)** undertook a study on maxim violations and flouting among subjects of an American political news interview. **Dixon and Spee (2003)** examined common perlocutionary acts and flouting of certain maxims among guests of a Belgian political and human interest talk show that featured personalities from divergent backgrounds and ideologies. **Zebua, Rukmini, and Saleh (2017)**, on the other hand, focused on certain episodes of the top-rating *The Ellen DeGeneres Show* and examined instances of following, flouting, and violating maxims among males and females, including the host Elle DeGeneres herself. Using De Generes' show also as a subject of their study, **Maharani, Mujiyanto, and Warsono (2020)** conducted a similar study; however, they included perlocutionary acts. **Putra (2014)** investigated the instances of maxim non-adherence in a CNN interview by British talk show host Piers Morgan, featuring international performing artist Beyonce Knowles-Carter. **Petersson (2015)** focused on closings done in two American talk shows as well as the hosts' adherence or non-adherence of maxims. Finally, **Petríčkova (2012)** compared instances of maxim adherence, flouting, and violation in light of politeness strategies as employed by guests in celebrity talk shows and institutional talk shows.

The current study is limited only to a particular radio-television program, "*Wanted sa Radyo*", hosted by eminent broadcaster Rafael "Raffy" Teshiba Tulfo together with veteran broadcaster and representative Rowena "Niña" Taduran and Tulfo's regular co-host Sharee Roman. The episodes are limited to those related to social issues.

Objectives

One of the objectives of the current study is to examine various perlocutionary acts in the speeches of all interlocutors in each episode. The second objective is to determine instances of adherence and violation of the Cooperative Principle among the interlocutors in sample episodes of "*Wanted sa Radyo*".

The current study intends to answer the following questions:

1. What are the prevalent perlocutionary acts found in public service programs?
2. What are the maxims within the Cooperative Principle that are being:
 - a. Followed
 - b. Violated

METHODS

Data description

The data used for the purpose of the current study consisted of two episodes of "*Wanted sa Radyo*". The first episode is entitled "Aplikante, nag-oral sex sa Colonel para makapasok sa PH Army?" and was aired on March 08, 2018; as for the second episode, it is entitled, "Wanted Sa Radyo Full Episode | September 4, 2019"; the last 15 minutes of the full episode focused on an issue involving the Department of Education-Region VII office and the mother of a teenaged male high school student who committed suicide after the boy's teacher accused him of an offense the former allegedly committed. Each of the episodes ran for a total of 14 to 20 minutes. One episode focused on a work-related issue while the other focused on an education-related issue. Both episodes were chosen based on the number of views on social media, particularly YouTube, and because they were among the trending episodes of "*Wanted sa Radyo*", having more than a million views. The first transcript consisted of 307 lines while the second consisted of only 75 lines.

Method of analysis

The researcher employed a mixed methodology in analyzing the data. Qualitative methods were done by transcribing and then analyzing every line for both perlocutionary acts and for maxim adherence or violation. For codification purposes, perlocutionary acts were codified by the researcher and were based on the intended effects on both speakers per utterance: a) Persuading the guests to elicit replies (PER); b) Convincing guests to tell the truth (CNV); c) Scaring interlocutors who fail to reply (SCR); d) Insulting interlocutors for their mistakes (INS); e) Get interlocutors to deliver results swiftly (GDS); f) Comforting interlocutors to appease them (COM); g) Inspiring interlocutors to establish solidarity (INP); and, h) Amusing interlocutors to humor them (AMU). Focusing on the quantitative analysis, frequency counting and percentages were employed by the researcher by obtaining the number and percentage of perlocutionary acts per line as well as the number of adherences and violations of the Cooperative Principle maxims as outlined by **Grice (1975)**: a) Maxim of Quality (pertaining to confirmed veracity of utterances); b) Maxim of Quantity (pertaining to the amount of information necessary); c) Maxim of Manner (pertaining to the use of words and the tone in delivery); and, d) Maxim of Relevance (pertaining to the connection of utterances within an exchange).

Procedures undertaken

The first step that the researcher did was to select two trending episodes of "*Wanted sa Radyo*" as posted on Youtube. He then transcribed each episode manually and with the aid of a free but limited online transcription website that had Tagalog as one of the languages. He then created codes pertaining to both perlocutionary acts and cooperative principle adherences and violations, using three to four letters for every code. He also labeled the episodes as EP-1 for the first episode and EP-2 for the second episode. Then the researcher analyzed the transcripts and labelled every line according to perlocutionary act and to maxim adherence or violation. Finally, he tabulated the results according to transcript.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

1. What are the prevalent perlocutionary acts found in public service programs?

Table 1

Perlocutionary acts in public service programs

PERLOCUTIONARY ACT	Episode 1 (Work-related)		Episode 2 (Education-related)	
	n	%	n	%
1. Persuading the guests to elicit replies (PER)	128	42%	23	31%
2. Convincing guests to tell the truth (CNV)	112	36%	34	45%
3. Scaring interlocutors who fail to reply (SCR)	0	0%	0	0%
4. Insulting interlocutors for their mistakes (INS)	4	1%	2	3%
5. Get interlocutors to deliver results swiftly (GDS)	21	7%	5	7%
6. Comforting interlocutors to appease them (COM)	2	1%	0	0%
7. Inspiring interlocutors to establish solidarity (INP)	22	7%	8	11%
8. Amusing interlocutors to humor them (AMU)	18	6%	0	0%
9. Combination of two or more	0	0%	3	4%
Total	307	100%	75	100%

The table above depicts the different perlocutionary acts prevalent across both episodes. As seen in the results above, the most prevalent perlocutionary acts are persuading (PER) and convincing (CNV). The results on perlocutionary acts are similar to the results of research by **Sobhani and Saghebi (2014)**, **Tressyalina and Ridwan (2015)** and **Dixon and Spee (2003)**. The results of the current study are also in agreement with those of **Karmila, Rohmana, and Aderlaepe (2019)** and of **Maharani, Mujiyanto, and Warsono (2020)**, since the talk shows that the researchers have used are almost similar in format as that of the show used in the current study.

One of the possible reasons behind the results could be that, being classified as institutional talk, "*Wanted sa Radyo*" mainly involves question and answers, with the hosts asking probing questions and the guests- consisting of complainants, respondents, and other resource persons- answering questions. The perlocutionary effect of persuading refers to the hosts' desired effect, which is inveigling their guests to answer their questions and to be truthful in their statements. As for the convincing effect, the desired effects that the guests want to achieve in their interlocutors (the hosts), are to believe their statements and to accept their statements with understanding, regardless of whether the guests are actually being veracious in their statements or not. A second reason could be that guests want to convince the hosts that they are right and firm in their statements despite being contradicted by the party opposing them (e.g. respondent versus complainant and vice versa). A third reason could be that respondents want to contradict what the opposite parties (complainants) are saying about them and the incidents in

order to save face, to avoid responsibility and accountability, to present themselves positively, and to ensure that the audience and the hosts would provide credence to their version of the issue being directed towards them.

The sample exchange below presents instances of persuading and convincing as perlocutionary acts, as exemplified between the main host and a respondent in an issue involving sexual harassment of an applicant:

46. RT (*PER*)

Col., andito po si Mr. Sanchez, kilala n'yo po siya?

47. CRM (*CNV*)

Opo, sir. Opo, sir.

48. RT (*PER*)

Meron po siyang alegasyon. Uhm, sabi po niya, sir, eh, lumapit po sa inyo para humingi ng tulong makapasa po...

49. CRM (*CNV*)

Opo, sir.

(EP-1, par. 46 to 49)

In the exchange above between the main host (RT) and the respondent (CRM), RT persuaded CRM to admit if he knew Mr. Sanchez (the complainant). CRM responded in the affirmative, therefore convincing RT that he actually knew the complainant personally. RT also persuaded CRM to explain his side on the issue raised by the complainant, which was on CRM's offer to the complainant to give him fellatio in exchange for an easier method of being accepted as a trainee soldier. As seen in the transcript above, CRM convinced RT that he would be elucidating his version of the issue as well as the subsequent events that happened.

The next transcript below presents the exchange between the host and the complainant, which also presents the perlocutionary acts of persuading and convincing:

102. RT (*PER*)

(To AS) Bakit sa gano'ng paraan mo binenta 'yung puri mo? Mali ka din doon.

103. AS (*CNV*)

(To RT) Opo. Mali din po ako.

104. RT (*PER*)

(To AS) 'Di mo siya puwedeng isisi. 'Yung sisi, 'di mo puwedeng ibigay kay (Col. Migote), 'di mo puwedeng ibunton sa kanya ang lahat. Meron ka ring kasalanan doon.

105. AS (*CNV*)

(To RT) Opo.

(EP-1, par. 102 to 105)

The exchange above depicts RT's first utterance as having the perlocutionary act of persuading. In this case, he persuaded AS (the complainant) to provide reasons behind his agreement to CRM's persistence for AS to give CRM

fellatio as part of CRM's promise to AS to accept him as a trainee soldier, CRM being a deputy officer of the Human Rights Office of the Armed Forces of the Philippines. As for AS, his response to RT's question had the perlocutionary act of convincing because he convinced RT that he has expressed regret in choosing convenience over sacrifice in undergoing the application process for trainee soldiers. RT's second utterance, also having the perlocutionary act of persuading, depicted RT's wanting AS to reflect on his other mistake, which is to desire to circumvent the standard procedures of applying to be a soldier. AS' response to RT's question reflects his desire to convince RT (and the audience) that he has regretted his decision to commit a transgression.

Shown below is a sample exchange from Episode 2:

47. RT (*PER*)

Eh, eh, Ma'am, Madam Secretary! Ang tanong ko lang po, ang tanong ko lang po sa sitwasyon. `Yun bang guro ay uutusan ang kanyang eskuwe, er, estudyante na bumili ng bottled water during school hours at walang lisensya, pinag-motor. Meron po bang violation doon o wala, sa senaryong `yon?

48. LMB (*CONV*)

Uh, dapat, uh, apparently, sa pagkakakuwento mo, uh, mukhang hindi dapat `yan gawin. Kaya nga, ipapa-verify ko pa, sir. Kasi ang mga bata, hindi naman natin `yan inuutusan.

(EP-2, par. 47 to 48)

In the exchange shown above, RT's utterance as belonging to the perlocutionary act of persuading served two purposes, one of which was to persuade his interlocutor- Department of Education Secretary Leonor Magtolis-Briones (referred to as LMB)- to comprehend the context of the issue being featured (in the case of Episode 2, a Grade 9 student committing suicide after being berated by his teacher through a post on social media). The other purpose was to force LMB to answer his question, which was on the possible violations by the teacher featured in the complaint. As for LMB's utterance, which belongs to the perlocutionary act of convincing, LMB's purposes behind her utterance was to make RT believe that she agrees with him and to let RT know that her department is investigating the case and the events that transpired.

Apart from the perlocutionary acts of persuading (*PER*) and convincing (*CON*), instances of the perlocutionary acts of insulting (*INS*), getting to do something (*GDS*), and amusing (*AMU*) are found in the exchange below:

61. RT (*INS*)

So, `di pa raw sigurado, sir. Sayang `yung pagtsupa n`ya sa inyo kung `di siya siguradong maging sundalo daw. Parang ganoon po ang dating n`yan.

62. CRM (*PER*)

(Laughs hard) Lokong bata, kausapin ko nga po para, uh---

63. RT (*GDS*)

Ayan, sir, mag-usap na kayo, sir. Sige, kausapin mo siya.

64. CRM (*AMU*)

(Laughs) Lokong bata 'to.

(EP-1, par. 61-64)

The exchange above shows RT's first utterance as an insult, which is inadvertent, given the circumstances within the episode as well as the context of the complaint. His use of the word *pagtsupa*, which is the Filipino slang term for fellatio, provides credence to the labeling of his utterance as an insult since it is generally unacceptable in mainstream media to use sex-related slang terms, especially in Philippine media, because viewers and listeners consist not only of adults but also minors. RT's motive was ostensibly for CRM to feel insulted by using a vulgar term and by echoing what CRM did to the complainant. As for RT's second utterance, its effect was for CRM to communicate verbally with the complainant, which CRM did only after persuasion by RT. Instead of CRM answering in the affirmative, he attempted to lighten the situation and the atmosphere through his utterance, coupled with a laugh before it.

Another instance of insulting as a perlocutionary act, which is intended to elicit shame from interlocutors, is found below:

29. RT

Sir, sir! Sandali lang, sir! Pastilan in tawon ginoo puwerde jud in pagka-bobo nimo, sir! Nganong nahimo ka na principal diha kung bobo ka? Pasaylo a ako, sir, pasaylo a ako, sir. Pero pag, pwerdeng pagka-bobo nimo, sir! Nganong kinahanglan pa ng DepEd order para magsuspindi ang isang principal ng isang guro na very glaring po yung ginawa niyang violation, which is hindi mo utusan 'yung estudyante mo na bumili ng tubig para sa 'yo gamit-gamit ang motor at ang estudyanteng ito ay walang lisensya! (long pause) Pastilan, ginoo! Kusog jud ang imong pagka-bobo! Principal, sir! Pasaylo ako, sir, ha, you don't deserve to be a principal! Even these DepEd people I am talking to right now, maayo na kamong nasa Cebu, pag-untogon ko ang imong mga kabobohang ulo!

(EP-2, par. 29)

The utterance above by RT was directed toward the principal of a school that was the subject of a complaint by the parent of the involved student who committed suicide. The following effects were observed in the utterance: a) to make the principal feel insulted and guilty over his inability to be accountable for his teacher's violations, b) to let the principal feel regret over his incompetence, and c) to let the principal feel fear over RT's threat to castigate him and the Department of Education-Region VII officials and staff further into submission.

The subsequent results pertaining to maxim adherence and violation are found in the second research question.

2. What are the maxims within the Cooperative Principle that are being commonly:

- a. Followed
- b. Violated

2.1. Followed maxims

Table 2.

Commonly followed Gricean maxims within the Cooperative Principle (CP)

ADHERED MAXIMS WITHIN CP	Episode 1 (Work-related)		Episode 2 (Education-related)	
	n	%	n	%
1. Manner (FMNR)	52	21%	23	44%
2. Relevance (FREL)	102	42%	7	13%
3. Quality (FQLT)	42	17%	15	29%
4. Quantity (FQNT)	48	20%	7	13%
5. Combination	1	0%	0	0%
Total	245	100%	52	100%

Table 2 presents the commonly adhered maxims on the part of the hosts and of the guests. Based on the results above, the maxims with the most number of adherences are relevance (for both Episodes 1 and 2) and manner, followed by quality and quantity. The results are consistent with those of **Petríčková (2012)**, **Tressyalina and Ridwan (2015)**, **Putra (2014)**, and **Petersson (2015)**, in which the three aforementioned maxims were adhered to. Petríčková’s study focused on the adherences of the Gricean maxims, which were done by the hosts and the guests of the featured shows in the study as part of their desire to establish rapport and camaraderie in spite of the seriousness of certain topics. Tressyalina and Ridwan’s research focused on guests’ adherence to most Gricean maxims, which is somewhat similar to the results of the current study, since the guests featured in the second episode of “Wanted sa Radyo” utilized for the study were DepEd-Region VII staffs, a school principal, and then-DepEd Secretary Leonor Magtolis-Briones herself. Putra’s Gricean maxims analysis revealed the adherence to maxims by the guest of CNN host Piers Morgan’s television show, singer-songwriter Beyonce Knowles-Carter herself, not only due to her desire to display professionalism in communication but also due to Ms. Carter’s intention of connecting with viewers of Morgan’s program. As for Petersson’s study, it focused on the hosts’ instances of maxim adherence, which occurred more than maxim violation, ostensibly due to the hosts’ following of the sequences and the scripts of the respective episodes.

The results of the study are in contrast to those by **Fadhly (2012)**, **Mustapha (2017)**, **Febriyani (2019)**, and **Hirsh (2015)**, which all focused on talk shows, which were mostly political. Generally, the results across the five studies reveal that even television show hosts have fewer instances of maxim adherence, mainly due to their desire to dominate the discussion, to assert their identities as media personalities even to guests of higher rank, and to extract answers from their guests, including political leaders, with little to no regard for guests’ personal space, broadcasting etiquette, and propriety in communicating with high-ranking officials.

One of the possible reasons behind the results could be that the hosts and the guests are expected to represent themselves and their respective institutions positively through mature, proper, and civil behavior. Second, it could be that talk shows such as "*Wanted sa Radyo*" are limited in terms of time and that the program features not only one issue but three, therefore enabling the staff of the program to budget the time and to expect the guests, and the hosts, to be forthright in their statements to save time and to allow further questions from the hosts. A third reason could be that complainants and respondents, as well as resource persons, are expected to be veracious and circumspect in their statements especially when being asked about their version of the issues being discussed.

Adherence to the maxims of quality (FQLT) and quantity (FQNT) are shown below, as reflected in the following exchanges between hosts:

3. NT (*FQLT*)

Istrikong patnubay at gabay ang kailangan po para sa mga bata. `Yon.

4. RT (*FQLT*)

Para sa mga bata, mga magulang. Seryoso po ako, seryoso po ako. Uhm, please paalisin n'yo po muna, `wag n'yo munang papanoorin. At kung may mga bata po sa inyo, patayin n'yo po ang radyo, patayin n'yo ang TV n'yo.

5. NT (*FQNT*)

Oo.

6. RT (*FQLT*)

Uhm, wala hong malisya rito. Ganito kami sa Wanted sa Radyo. Uhm, hindi scripted 'to.

(EP-1, par. 3-6)

In the exchange above, the hosts RT and NT (referring to Niña Taduran) observe the maxim of quality because they forewarned the audience, especially parents, of the sensitive nature and mature theme of the featured episode, which was about a deputy officer of the Human Rights Office forcing an applicant to fellate his penis in exchange for the applicant's instant admission as a trainee soldier. NT informed the audience that the topic was to be rated SPG (Strict Parental Guidance) since the episode would be replete with the guests' narrations of workplace-related sexual transgressions. RT further stated that the show would consist of unscripted conversations and would involve conversations with the complainant (AS) and with the respondent (CRM). In doing so, as viewed by the hosts, authenticity would be elicited more if interviews were to be done in a somewhat spontaneous manner but with adherence to the time limit of the interview and to the topic of the interview, thus avoiding more instances of maxim flouting among interviewers and interviewees.

Instances of adherence to the maxims of relevance (FREL), as well as quality (FQLT) and quantity (FQNT), are depicted below, as seen in the exchanges between the main host (RT) and the complainant (AS) and between RT and the respondent (CRM):

30. RT (*FREL*)

'Di, bakit nagkaroon po kayo ng ganyang ugnayan?

31. AS (*FQLT*)

Humihingi po sana ako ng tulong sa kanya para tulungan po akong makapasa sa neuro or makapag-apply sa iba...makapasa po.

32. RT (*FREL*)

Gusto mong maging sundalo?

33. AS (*FQNT*)

Opo.

(EP-1, par. 30-33)

242. RT (*FMNR*)

Pe, pero sir, halimbawa, hiniling niya. Eh kayo po, colonel, you know better. Sana po mataas ang standards ninyo, 'yung integridad ninyo. Sabihin mo, "Ayokong mag, ayokong ipasubo ko 'yung titi ko sa 'yo. Colonel ako, ikaw, magti-training pa lang. Ba't kita papatulan?" Ba't mo pinatulan, sir?

243. CRM (*FQLT*)

Uh, pasensiya ka na po, sir.

244. RT (*FREL*)

'Di ba, sir?

245. CRM (*FQLT*)

Opo, sir. Tama po kayo, sir.

(EP-1, par. 242-245)

As shown in the two exchanges, both CRM and AS, who were the guests in the first episode, adhered to the maxims of quality. In the case of the first exchange, AS followed the maxim of quality by admitting that he sought the help of CRM in passing the neurological examination and other examinations needed to become a trainee soldier. As for CRM, he also complied with the maxim of quality by asserting that RT was right in admonishing him about his transgression against AS and by admitting that he was responsible for his error towards AS. RT adhered to the maxim of relevance by asking follow-through questions, which were meant to help AS to clarify his statement and to enable CRM to reflect on his misdeed.

The following exchanges from Episode 2 also depict compliance with the maxim of manner (*FMNR*) along with the maxims of quantity and quality:

12. RT (*FMNR*)

Ma'am, Ma'am, sandali lang po. 'Yun pong eskwelahan, umamin na po, maging 'yung teacher. And yet, inutusan nya talaga yung bata na bumili ng bottled water during school hours.

13. DSS (*FQNT*)

Yes, sir.

14. RT (FMNR)

Okay? At yung bata’y walang lisensya. Doon palang, ma’am, may problema na agad sa guro. Dapat may sanction na agad po doon. (to Mr. Joel Roxas) Mr. Joel Rojas, Principal, magandang hapon po. Mr. Roxas?

15. JR (FMNR)

Magandang hapon po.

(EP-2, par. 12-15)

39. RT (FMNR)

Opo, opo. Sa Cebu. Inutusan po ito...inutusan po `yung bata, 15 years old, na bumili po ng dalawang galon na bottled water.

40. LMB (FQLT)

Oo.

41. RT (FQLT)

During school hours.

42. LMB (FQLT)

Oo, oo.

(EP-2, par. 39-42)

In the first exchange above, both RT (as the host) and JR (as the respondent, actually a representative of the teacher) adhered to the maxim of manner. On the part of RT, he explained to the Department of Education-Region VII Staff (referred to as DSS) the situation perspicaciously and directly, which DSS agreed with. He also greeted JR, who in turn greeted him. Both adhered to the maxim of manner due to the respect, politeness, and cordiality they accorded to each other. Focusing on the second exchange, RT adhered to the maxim of manner by the use of the Filipino term “opo” and at the same time explained to LMB the issue being resolved. DSS and LMB adhered to the maxim of quality by agreeing to what RT told them instead of being defensive and removing themselves from their accountability as Department of Education employees.

The next item focuses on the violations committed by the interlocutors in the two episodes.

2.2. Violated maxims

Table 3.

Commonly violated Gricean maxims within the Cooperative Principle (CP)

VIOLATED MAXIMS WITHIN CP	Episode 1 (Work-related)		Episode 2 (Education-related)	
	n	%	N	%
1. Manner (VMNR)	46	74%	16	70%
2. Relevance (VREL)	4	6%	0	0%

3. Quality (VQLT)	8	13%	3	13%
4. Quantity (VQNT)	4	6%	4	17%
5. Combination	0	0%	0	0%
Total	62	100%	23	100%

Table 3 illustrates the commonly violated maxims across the episodes used in the study. Based on the results, a majority of the violations were those related to the maxims of manner, followed by quality (VQLT) and quantity (VQNT). The results of the current study under violations are consistent with those of the studies by **Clementson (2018)**, **Rosyidah (2013)**, **Fadhly (2012)**, **Yang (2014)**, **Dixon and Spee (2003)**, **Putra (2014)**, **Zebua, Rukimini, and Saleh (2017)**, **Febriyani (2019)**, **Hirsh (2015)**, and **Sobhani and Saghebi (2014)**. However, the results of the current study are in contrast to those by **Petričková (2012)**, in which there were more instances of violations and flouting of maxims through negative politeness strategies among hosts and guests of institutional talk shows. Focusing on media-related maxim flouting on the part of politicians, the research studies by **Dixon and Spee (2003)** and by **Clementson (2018)** revealed political talk show guests’ flouting of maxims, similar to the results generated by the study by **Febriyani (2019)**, in which Turkiye President Recep Tayyip Erdogan attempted to be evasive and domineering in the interview in which he was the sole guest, ostensibly due to his wielding of his political influence and his status as the head of state and government. Hirsch’s research, in terms of its results, revealed politicians’ proclivities to use sarcasm, irony, and other figures of speech in their attempts to dominate discussions, similar to the study by Yang.

A first reason behind the results could be the use of vulgar terms on the part of one of the interlocutors to narrate an event graphically. Second, it could be deduced that some of the interlocutors’ desire to circumvent their statements and to add or delete information as a way of concealing the truth in their statements. Third, a possible reason could be the use of sarcasm and profanity as a way of expressing disgust and frustration at the non-compliance of some of the interlocutors with being responsible for their neglect and transgressions.

The following excerpts depict the violation of the maxim of manner (VMNR):

24. RT (*FMNR*)

Okay. Meron kayong reklamo laban kay Col. Rogelio Migote, deputy Human Rights office ng Philippine Army. Ano po’ng reklamo n’yo kay Col. Migote? Nakiking po siya, naka-monitor na po. Sige po, ikuwento n’yo po, sir.

25. AS (*VMNR*)

Yung pinahawak n’ya po sa ‘kin ‘yung titi niya. Tapos---

26. RT (*FMNR*)

Lapit po sa mikropono.

27. AS (*VMNR*)

Pinatsupa po n’ya sa ‘kin.

(EP-1, par. 24-27)

21. RT (*VMNR*)

(to DSS; raising his voice) Ma'am, ito pong gagawin ko, trust me. Ipatatawag po namin kayo sa Congress, okay? May way po kami. Kayo po d'yan sa DepEd Cebu, tingnan natin kung 'yung kabobohan niyo, subukan n'yong mamilosopo sa Kongreso. Kasama ka siguro diyan, ayaw mong magsalita at magbigay ng pangalan. Lahat kayo diyan sa DepEd 7, Region 7, trust me! Baka a week or two nasa...nasa Congress kayo sa Maynila! Mga punyeta kayong bobo kayo! Pinapa-high blood n'yo ako sa kabobohan n'yo! Tuloy. 'yung mga Cebung matatalino, mga taga-Cebu, nadadamay sa inyo, eh! Ang bobo n'yo!

22. JR (*FMNR*)

Hello, sir?

(EP-2, par. 21-22)

68. RT (*VMNR*)

Masuspindi na 'yung teacher mo. Okay na? Mm. Hirit ka pa? (to DSS) Regional director's office Cebu? Ma'am?

69. DSS (*FMNR*)

Yes, sir?

70. RT (*FMNR*)

Nakikinig po kayo?

71. DSS (*FMNR*)

Yes po, opo.

(EP-2, par. 68-71)

In the first exchange, AS (the complainant) violated the maxim of manner by using graphic, vulgar terms for fellatio and penis, ostensibly due to his familiarity with the terms "tit" (penis) and "pinatsupa" (fellated a man's penis). Another reason could be his vivid recall of his experience with the respondent CRM. On the other hand, in the second exchange, the violation of the maxim of manner by RT could be attributed to his frustration over the ostensible circumvention by JR and DSS of the complaint against the teacher responsible for shaming the student who committed suicide and to his disgust over the incompetence of the resource person (DSS) and of the respondent (JR) in their duties. And focusing on the third exchange, RT violated the maxim of manner through his use of sarcasm towards both JR, as the principal of the school involved, and DSS, as the staff member of the school division to which the school belongs.

In summary, violations of maxims were generally discovered to have occurred less than adherence to maxims. One of the possible reasons behind the prevalence of maxim adherence could be the structured nature of public service programs, which tend to follow a script for sequencing and continuity purposes, especially "Wanted Sa Radyo", which is aired live within a two-hour timeslot. Secondly, adherence to maxims ensures that respect is maintained among hosts and guests despite the occurrence of verbalized conflicts, especially whenever there are other guests who are pitted against each other; in this case, these are the complainant and the respondent. On the part of the hosts, since they moderate and facilitate the flow of the television-radio show, they are expected to dominate the conversation

not to asseverate their expertise on the featured topics but to control instances of unexpected outbursts, arguments, and other similar verbal conflicts between or among guests. Thirdly, maxim adherence is manifested among the guests, perhaps because they have been oriented earlier by production staff members before the airing of the episodes and in order for them to adhere to the time limit given to each segment. Finally, violations of maxims were less prevalent, ostensibly due to the respect accorded by the hosts to the guests and the guests to the hosts, which is expected of interlocutors on live television and/or radio, and even on social media, despite having differences not only in terms of versions of events involving the guests but also in terms of hosts' schemata of the issues presented in the episodes.

CONCLUSION

The current study focused on the perlocutionary acts and on the maxims under the Cooperative Principle that are being followed and violated, in the context of a Philippine public service program. Based on the results of the study, a majority of the utterances are of the persuading and convincing types of perlocutionary acts, due to the question-and-answer nature of exchange prevalent in public service programs. Persuading as a perlocutionary act and effect can be manifested in the form of inveigling an interlocutor to answer a question, to tell the truth, and to confess to one's transgressions, while convincing can be in the form of forcing interlocutors to believe one's statement, of getting interlocutors to listen to one's version of events, and of letting interlocutors consider an opposing party's statement as a lie. In terms of the prevalently adhered maxims, relevance and manner were the maxims being followed, in part due to the interlocutors' desire to solve issues and the public, civil nature of public service programs. On the other hand, the most violated maxim was on manner, which was attributed to guests' desire to circumvent their statements, to one of the hosts' frustration over the respondents' and resource persons' moves in evading accountability for the issues at hand, and the use of vulgarity and sarcasm.

One of the implications for teaching is that maxims must be taught across all subjects and courses, especially those related to communication, in order that students be able to adhere to them in all their exchanges, regardless of who their interlocutors may be. A second implication for teaching is that theories related to sociolinguistics, discourse analysis, and pragmatics must be applied to research related to mass media, especially those that focus on public, social issues. Third, inculcating conventions of communication and maxims in teaching communication and social skills must be done by educators in order that positive exchanges are fostered. Finally, communicative strategies must be widely taught and applied both in school and at the workplace as part of one's development of competencies related to one's professional and social lives.

An implication for media practice and policy implementation could be that hosts must be reminded of their roles as facilitators in live broadcasts, which must focus attention on the guests and the topics featured. A second implication is for regulatory bodies such as the Kapisanan ng mga Brodkaster ng Pilipinas (KBP), the National Telecommunications Commission (NTC), Movie and Television Review and Classification Board (MTRCB), and other related agencies to implement more stringent guidelines in handling sensitive topics with tact, decency, diplomacy, and high regard for viewer sensibilities so that viewership of public service programs and other similar productions

would not be adversely affected, notably when complaints over hosts' and/or guests' use of undesirable language and display of insensitive behaviors are sent to government and private agencies related to media management and regulation, such as the NTC and KBP. Finally, aspiring and veteran media practitioners, especially broadcasters, must also be oriented and trained on practicing ethicality and civility in their interactions with guests and fellow hosts both during live and pre-recorded productions, whether on television or radio, especially because there are productions that are also aired live on social media platforms.

It is recommended that future researchers utilize more samples of public service shows, particularly those related to categories such as domestic issues, criminality, medical issues, and other related categories, in order to determine a more conclusive and cohesive pattern in terms of perlocutionary acts used and of maxims and their adherence, flouting, and violation. Other programs related to public service may be used for comparison and for determining other patterns in terms of the aforementioned aspects of research. Future research may also focus on politeness strategies, transitivity analysis, and gender and power relations. Politeness strategies and face-saving strategies may also be used in future research on public service programs.

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